

NATURAL FLAVONES. PART V. FURTHER OBSERVATIONS ON THE CONSTITUTION OF GARDENIN AND TAMBULIN

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Gardenin does not couple with diazotised *p*-nitraniline and its methyl ether is not identical with hibiscetin heptamethyl ether (3 : 5 : 7 : 8 : 3' : 4' : 5'-heptamethoxyflavone). Hence gardenin must be formulated as 3 : 6 : 8 : 3' : 4' : 5'-hexamethoxy-5-hydroxyflavone. Tambulin dimethyl ether has been found to be identical with pentamethylherbacetin, but not with tangeretin. Hence tambulin is 3 : 8 : 4'-trimethoxy-5 : 7-dihydroxyflavone.

As the result of a detailed examination of gardenin, the colouring matter of Dikamali gum, Bose and Nath (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 138) advanced two alternative formulae (I and II) for the compound. Based on these structures the dihydroxy- ω -methoxyacetoquinone, obtained by alkaline degradation of gardenin, was assigned the structures (III) or (IV), which can be derived from (I) and (II) respectively.

The properties of this quinone, which behaved like a dibasic acid, have been found to be very similar to those of 2 : 5-dihydroxyquinones in general and pedicinin in particular. Pedicinin has been shown to be a quinone having the structure (V) (Bose and Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 499). Based on this analogy the structure (III) appears most plausible for the quinone from gardenin which should consequently be regarded as having the formula (I).

Hydroxyflavones, having a free *para* or *ortho* position to an OH group, are capable of coupling with diazo salts. This property, according to Prof. K. Venkataraman (*private communication*), might be utilised in locating unsubstituted positions in the benzene ring of the pyrone nucleus. An inspection of the formula (I) shows that it has no free positions *ortho* or *para* to the solitary OH group in position 5, whereas formula (II) is expected to

furnish an azo compound in view of the absence of a substituent in position 6. An attempt was therefore made to couple gardenin with diazotised *p*-nitraniline following the procedure described by Mahal and Venkataraman (*Curr. Sci.*, 1938, 6, 450). Gardenin failed to produce an azo compound. The author therefore felt inclined to assign structure (I) to gardenin.

A more convincing proof against formula (II) has now been furnished by Prof. T. R. Seshadri (*private communication*) who has shown that heptamethylhibiscetin (VI) is not identical with methylgardenin. Hence formula (II) for gardenin is ruled out. Gardenin consequently must have the formula (I).

Regarding the constitution of tambulin, the colouring matter of *Xanthoxylum acanthopodium* DC. (Bose and Bose, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 183) the formula (VII) was proposed after a careful examination of its properties and degradation products, and after proving that tambulin dimethyl ether is different from tangeretin (Nelson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 1392). The corroboration of this view has now been made possible

by a direct comparison between herbacetin pentamethyl ether (VIII) and tambulin dimethyl ether. A specimen of the former was placed at our disposal by Professor Seshadri, to whom we offer our best thanks. This ether was found to melt at 157°, and a mixture of this substance and tambulin dimethyl ether (m.p. 160°, after high vacuum distillation) melted at 158-59°. The identity of tambulin dimethyl ether with (VIII) is thus established and consequently tambulin must be formulated as (VII).